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Abstract—Time dispersion of the radio channel is an important characteristic in waveform and other system design of wireless communication links. In this TD we present delay spreads and maximum excess delays analysed using data from single directional propagation measurements at 140 GHz radio frequency in both outdoor and indoor environments. Since upper mm-wave radio links necessitate high antenna gains, we consider beam steered radio channel as the basis of our analysis, i.e., beam gains are multiplied with the measured propagation path gains prior to the analysis. Preliminary results show 1.5–11 ns median rms delay spreads and 23–110 ns median values of maximum excess delays, depending on the LOS/NLOS condition, environment, link distance, and used beam width.

Index Terms—Beamforming, delay spread, D-band radio channel, time dispersion.

I. INTRODUCTION

Extending to upper millimetre wave (mm-wave) and terahertz (THz) radio frequencies is expected to make extremely high data rate communication becoming reality in 6G era [1]. High gain antennas and antenna arrays are necessary to compensate for the severe signal attenuation at high frequency [2]. New radio interfaces must be designed and parameterized for future communication systems. Such work is ongoing, e.g., in the European Hexa-X project [3]. In particular the waveform design is related to time dispersion of the radio channel. E.g., the sub-carrier spacing, the cyclic prefix (CP) length, or the equalizer length are determined based on the expected time dispersion, i.e., propagation excess delays of the radio channel.

Note that the radiation pattern of an antenna array strongly depends on the beamforming scheme, antenna elements, and the geometry of the array. Thus, different beam patterns will formulate different radio channels when either the concentrated beams are steered at the desired directions or some more complex beamforming is used.

From radio wave propagation perspective, due to the combination of weighted multipath components (MPCs) from selected directions, the beamformed channels will perform

different angular and delay dispersion characteristics in comparison with the omni-directional channels. Experimental and simulation results have revealed the spatial sparse nature of high-frequency channels, which benefits beam management in exploiting low-complexity methods [4]. However, there is a lack of studies that focus on analyzing the beam pattern impact on multipath delay spread (DS), which is related to the coherence bandwidth of the channel.

A high delay spread causes inter-symbol interference (ISI), which can be mitigated by inserting CP before data symbols. The robustness against ISI in high-frequency multi-carrier systems is determined by the length of CP, where in general longer symbols is adopted in the environments with larger DS [5]. Similarly, in single carrier systems with time-domain equalization, delay spread determine the required length of the equalizer. At the expense of lower spectral efficiency and longer transmission delay, optimizing waveform design strongly depends on the multipath DS of the radio channel [6].

The narrower the beam the less MPCs can be detected, corresponding to the decrease of root mean squared (RMS) DS. Theoretical analysis indicates that there are several beamforming attributes, including antenna size, half power beam width (HPBW), side-lobe level, beam direction, and beam misalignment, that affect the DS [6], [7]. In [8], a comparison of the measured DS at 2.45 GHz in an indoor obstructed environment shows that co-polarized directional antenna pairs provide smaller DS than omni-directional antenna pairs. Similar results have been observed also on the 5–60 GHz channel measurements, where the reduction of DS as a function of HPBW becomes more obvious in outdoor environments with relatively larger DSs [9]. The aforementioned empirical analyses, in general, are promoted directly based on the field measurements using the antennas with different HPBWs. Moreover, high-resolution directional channel sounding were conducted and the synthetic antenna patterns with variable beamwidths are applied in post-processing at 28 GHz [10] and 60 GHz [11], [12]. This method decouples the antennas and the propagation channel using beamforming technique for the purpose of evaluating its impact on the DS. However, the directional DS is calculated based on the power delay profile (PDP), which is synthesized from the power angular delay profile (PADP) within a certain angular range. The corresponding range is determined by the HPBW of antenna and towards the direction providing the highest received power.

This paper characterizes the beam effect on multipath delay spread based on the indoor and outdoor directional channel sounding data measured in D-band, more specifically at 140–

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Fig. 1. Antenna locations of the first measurement campaign in the entrance hall.

Fig. 2. Antenna locations of the second measurement campaign in the entrance hall.

145 GHz radio frequency. Best potential beam directions are identified using the method developed in [13]. Then DSs of the omni-directional case, the highest gain beam direction case, and all potential beam directions, are computed and compared. The purpose of this work is to provide statistical insight to the time dispersion radio channels for radio interface designers. Of course not forgetting the generally interesting accumulating understanding of upper mm-wave radio channel parameters.

II. D-BAND CHANNEL PROPAGATION DATA

The measurement data considered in this study are based on four indoor and three outdoor measurement campaigns. They were all obtained using a vector network analyzer (VNA) based sub-THz channel sounder. The Tx side has 0 dBi omnidirectional bicone antenna with 45° elevation HPBW while the Rx side has 19 dBi horn antenna with 10° azimuth HPBW and 40° elevation HPBW. The horn antenna was rotated in the azimuth plane while its main lobe was fixed at the horizontal plane. More details about the radio channel sounder and measurement process are elaborated in Sec. II-A in [14]. There are some differences in the measurements parameters used in each scenario as listed in Table I.

A. Indoor Measurement Campaign

The measurement campaigns performed in the shopping mall and airport check-in hall are described in [15]. The third indoor site, which is further described in [14], is in the entrance hall of the Electrical Engineering building of Aalto University in Maarintie 8, Espoo, Finland. Two measurement campaigns were performed in this site and are referred in Table I as Entrance Hall 1 and Entrance Hall 2. The antenna locations of the former and the latter measurement campaigns are shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, respectively.

B. Outdoor Measurement Campaign

The first outdoor measurement campaign was conducted in a suburban area along Maarintie and Konemiehentie, Otaniemi, Finland. The outside walls of the buildings in the area are mainly made up of bricks and have glass windows and doors with metallic frames. There are also few large metallic structures installed on the walls. Metallic posts, trees, and parking space with cars moving from time to time can also be

Fig. 3. Antenna locations of the measurement campaign in a suburban area. The blue, green, and cyan markers denote the Tx locations paired with Rx1, Rx2, and both Rx, respectively

found in the area. The antenna locations for this measurement campaign are shown in Fig. 3.

The second measurement campaign was performed in a residential environment along Leppavaarankatu, Espoo, Finland. The street is mostly surrounded by residential buildings and by some commercial buildings. Metallic street posts and trees can also be found in the area. The antenna locations for this residential area are shown in Fig. 4.

The last outdoor measurement campaign was performed in an urban environment in the city center along Aleksanterinkatu, Helsinki, Finland. The street is surrounded by commercial buildings on both sides, forming a street canyon. The street is primarily intended for pedestrians, blocking vehicular traffic except for trams. There are rare metallic sign posts found on the street. The location has heavy loads of pedestrians and has some vehicles that park on the side walks occasionally. The antenna locations for this residential area are shown in Fig. 5. Closely-spaced antenna locations were positioned at the building corners 1 and 2.

C. Data Post-processing

From measurements of a single Tx-Rx link, a power angular-delay (PADP) profile is obtained. The local peaks were then identified from the PADP leading to the sum of discrete multipaths as

$$P(\phi, \tau) = \sum_{n=1}^N G_n \delta(\phi - \phi_n^{\text{Rx}}) \delta(\tau - \tau_n), \quad (1)$$

TABLE I
MEASUREMENT CAMPAIGN DETAILS

Measurement Detail	Shopping Mall	Airport	Entrance Hall 1	Entrance Hall 2	Suburban	Residential	City Center
RF (GHz)	141.5-145.1	141.5-145.1	140-144	140-144	140-144	140-144	140-144
Tx Antenna Height (m)	1.89	1.7 above 2 nd floor	1.85	1.85	1.85	1.85	2.00
Rx Antenna Height (m)	1.89	2.1 above 3 rd floor	1.85	1.85	1.85	1.85	2.00
EIRP (dBm)	-12	-12	5	5	5	5	5
Rx Azimuth Range (°)	0-360	0-25, 245-360	40-250	-90-180 (Rx1); 40-250 (Rx2); 110-290 (Rx3)	0-355	Mostly 0-355	Mostly 0-355
Azimuth Step (°)	6	5	10	5	5	5	5
Number of LOS Links	16	10	2	12	32	13	19
Number of NLOS Links	2	1	9	56	8	42	21
Environment Type	Indoor	Indoor	Indoor	Indoor	Outdoor	Outdoor	Outdoor
Link Distance Range (m)	3-65	15-51	3-47	3-66	2-172	20-175	10-178

Fig. 4. Antenna locations of the measurement campaign in a residential area.

Fig. 5. Antenna locations of the measurement campaign in a city center.

where N is the number of paths, G_n , ϕ_n^{Rx} , and τ_n are the gain, measured azimuth angle-of-arrival, and delay of the n th path, respectively. Note that the antenna gains are de-embedded in Eq. (1) using radiation patterns of the horn and bicone antennas.

III. METHOD

In this section we describe the method of determining the RMS DS and the maximum excess delay (MED) of beam steered radio channel. Our initial data are discrete PADPs estimated from measurements, as discussed in Section II.

Fig. 6. Propagation paths, beam power and selected beam directions in an example link.

In the first step we steer a beam towards azimuth angle in $[0^\circ, 360^\circ]$ with the 1° increment. We use a synthetic 3GPP pattern with definable HPBW and peak to minimum gain ratio, as specified in Table 7.3-1 of [16]. The peak to minimum gain ratio and the HPBW are chosen to be 30 dB and 10° , respectively. It is important to notice that the radiation pattern does not have side lobes, and hence the resulting time dispersion parameters are probably smaller as compared to those with less ideal beam shapes.

With each steering angle α the propagation path gains are weighted with corresponding beam gains. Sum of weighted propagation path gains is the beam power toward azimuth angle α . The maximum of these beam powers indicates the *max beam* direction. Other prominent beams are included in *local maxima beams* (M1) if they satisfy two conditions: they are the local maxima of the beam power curve and they are within 10 dB dynamic range of the maximum beam power. Alternatively, other beams are included in the set *uncorrelated beams* (M2) if they satisfy the 10 dB dynamic range condition, and they provide less than 0.5 correlation with the max beam. An example power angular profile, beam power function, and beam selections are shown in Fig. 6. All other details, mathematics, and visualization of the process of identifying beam directions are given in [13].

Finally, the delay spread and the maximum excess delay are calculated based on beam weighted path gains for each considered beam in each of the measured links. A power threshold $\Delta = -30$ dB is used for beam weighted path gains in the DS and MED calculation. This power threshold has a substantial impact on both metrics and it must be chosen carefully. Here we used common practices in propagation channel analysis and considered also the expected modulation orders and signal to noise power ratio (SNR) requirements of envisioned D-band radio links.

A beam weighted discrete PDP is defined by path delays τ_n and squared magnitudes P_n , $n = 1, \dots, N$. Prior to calculating metrics, the power threshold is applied and all squared path gains below the threshold are set to 0, i.e., $P_n = 0$ if $P_n < \max_{n=1, \dots, N} P_n - \Delta$. The text book formula for RMS delay spread is

$$\tau_{\text{rms}} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{P_T} \sum_n P_n \tau_n^2 - \bar{\tau}^2}, \quad (2)$$

where the total power $P_T = \sum_n P_n$ and the mean delay $\bar{\tau} = \sum_n P_n \tau_n$. The mean excess delay, considering only paths within the power threshold Δ , is simply

$$\tau_{\text{med}} = \left(\max_{n \in [1, N] \wedge P_n > 0} \tau_n \right) - \left(\min_{n \in [1, N] \wedge P_n > 0} \tau_n \right). \quad (3)$$

IV. RESULTS

Analysis results are presented in this section. The power threshold is -30 dB in all cases. The HPBW is 10° in subsections IV-A and IV-B, while it varies in IV-C.

A. Delay Spread

Delay spreads τ_{rms} of all links are illustrated in Fig. 7. The first 157 links are outdoor and the remaining 132 are indoor. The *isotropic* DS curve denotes the case where no beam was formed and hence propagation paths are considered without any weighting by antenna effects. The *max beam* curve represents DS of each link when propagation paths are weighted with the beam pattern pointing towards the best possible direction, i.e., the direction providing the highest channel gain. Then *uncor beams* are DSs of the uncorrelated beams defined in Section III. As expected, the *max beam* DS is almost always below that of the *isotropic*. On the other hand, the other uncorrelated beams may provide even higher DSs in some occasions where the actual line of sight (LOS) path is not necessarily illuminated by the beam. LOS links are denoted by green squares in the figure.

Cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of delay spreads are depicted in Fig. 8. Different propagation conditions are separated in the figure. Indoor and outdoor measurement data are in the left and right figure, respectively. LOS and non-line of sight (NLOS) are plotted by the solid and dotted line type, respectively. NLOS condition is often an obstructed line of sight (OLOS) in the measured link. In this analysis we do not differentiate results between NLOS and OLOS. *LM beams* denotes the local maxima beams, as described in

Fig. 7. Delay spreads of all links. Green square denotes a LOS link.

Fig. 8. CDFs of delay spread on outdoor/indoor LOS/NLOS.

Section III. We can observe that the outdoor case contains many links, close to 20%, where beam steered DS equals zero. The max beam and LM beams have quite similar median DSs in both indoor and outdoor. The highest DSs can be found from outdoor data. The *isotropic* DSs are larger in the outdoor environment almost throughout the probability axis.

The distance dependency of the maximum beam DS is shown in Fig. 9. Evidently, outdoor links are longer and the highest DSs can be found among them. However, any clear tendency of DS vs. link distance cannot be observed. Surprisingly, NLOS DSs are not clearly higher than those of LOS links, except the few highest ones that can be found in NLOS links. Mean, median and 90th percentile DS statistics of links differentiated by the environment, propagation condition and link distance, are collected in Table II. Notice that there was neither indoor links with Tx-Rx spacing above 100 m nor outdoor links with below 10 m spacing. The number of measured links per environment, LOS/NLOS, and distance category is small in some cases. Therefore, the confidence of categorised statistics is not in all cases high.

B. Maximum Excess Delay

The maximum excess delay as defined in eq. (3) of all links on different beam alternatives is shown in Fig. 10. Definitions of the figure are analogous to the delay spread Fig. 7. The highest MEDs are among outdoor links, approaching close to

TABLE II
DS IN OUTDOOR/INDOOR AND LOS/NLOS AT DIFFERENT LINK DISTANCES. ALL VALUES ARE IN NANOSECOND UNIT.

			Link dist ≤ 10 m			10 m < link dist ≤ 100 m			Link dist > 100 m		
			mean	median	90-prctile	mean	median	90-prctile	mean	median	90-prctile
Indoor	LoS	Isotropic	8.5	7.6	12.6	26.7	20.8	56.9	-	-	-
		The max beam	4.5	3.4	9.5	9.6	7.1	19.0	-	-	-
		LM beams	4.3	3.3	9.3	11.9	8.2	28.6	-	-	-
	NLoS	Isotropic	19.9	21	38.7	28.2	24.5	46.2	-	-	-
		The max beam	2.0	1.6	4.4	12.6	9.4	27.4	-	-	-
		LM beams	2.8	1.6	8.6	16.2	9.6	38.8	-	-	-
Outdoor	LoS	Isotropic	-	-	-	29.4	26.1	57.0	19.1	18.4	39.6
		The max beam	-	-	-	9.3	4.7	23.8	8.0	10.3	16.8
		LM beams	-	-	-	11.8	6.6	25.3	10.0	10.9	24.1
	NLoS	Isotropic	-	-	-	55.8	33.3	141.7	28.4	16.1	85.7
		The max beam	-	-	-	19.2	5.4	65.2	7.4	0.0	25.6
		LM beams	-	-	-	22.9	10.4	68.4	11.6	1.5	29.3

Fig. 9. Delay spread vs. link distance on outdoor/indoor LOS/NLOS.

Fig. 11. CDFs of MED on outdoor/indoor LOS/NLOS.

Fig. 10. Maximum excess delays of all links. Green square denotes a LOS link.

700 ns in the maximum beam case. Corresponding max beam MEDs in indoor are always below 270 ns.

CDFs of maximum excess delays are depicted in Fig. 11. Indoor and outdoor measurement data are in the left and right figure, respectively. LOS and NLOS are plotted by the solid and dotted line type, respectively. *LM beams* denotes the local maxima beams, as described in Section III. In the outdoor case close to 20% of links contain only single path above the 30 dB

threshold and hence the beam steered MED equals zero. The same figure in the indoor case is approximately 2 %. The max beam and LM beams have quite similar median MEDs in both indoor and outdoor. The longest MEDs can be found from outdoor data. The *isotropic* MEDs are larger in the outdoor environment almost throughout the probability axis.

The distance dependency of the maximum beam MED is shown in Fig. 12. The largest MEDs are among outdoor links, but not in the links with longest Tx-Rx distance. By visual inspection one cannot find any strong correlation between MED and link distance. Surprisingly, NLOS MEDs are not clearly higher than those of LOS links. The highest MED in indoor is in a LOS link and four out of five largest MEDs in outdoor are from LOS links. Mean, median and 90th percentile MED statistics are collected in Table III.

C. Impact of Beam Width

In this sub-section we investigate the impact of HPBW on DS. Here all analysed links are treated without differentiating the environment or the propagation condition. CDFs of delay spreads of the maximum beam and the local maxima beams are illustrated in Fig. 13 and 14, respectively. As the HPBW decreases from 30° to 20°, 10°, and 5°, the CDF curve becomes shifted towards smaller DS values. This is the expected

TABLE III
MED IN OUTDOOR/INDOOR AND LOS/NLOS AT DIFFERENT LINK DISTANCES. ALL VALUES ARE IN NANOSECOND UNIT.

			Link dist \leq 10 m			10 m < link dist \leq 100 m			Link dist > 100 m		
			mean	median	90-prctile	mean	median	90-prctile	mean	median	90-prctile
Indoor	LoS	Isotropic	98.6	71.7	209.6	204.4	165.7	377.1	-	-	-
		The max beam	57.2	68.6	99.6	99.4	92.1	199.6	-	-	-
		LM beams	60.3	68.6	113.4	117.8	101.5	232.2	-	-	-
	NLoS	Isotropic	184.6	183.1	301.4	191.6	181.0	314.6	-	-	-
		The max beam	25.6	23.3	38.1	94.1	85.4	202.0	-	-	-
		LM beams	42.4	22.9	140.1	112.9	97.4	220.6	-	-	-
Outdoor	LoS	Isotropic	-	-	-	363.0	357.4	583.8	232.8	256.6	403.9
		The max beam	-	-	-	140.4	61.6	403.3	94.9	75.5	286.0
		LM beams	-	-	-	154.8	106.6	370.6	111.5	105.2	287.7
	NLoS	Isotropic	-	-	-	290.1	283.5	510.4	128.4	72.3	373.5
		The max beam	-	-	-	119.1	59.5	285.6	65.7	6.6	255.0
		LM beams	-	-	-	180.0	110.1	449.4	94.7	26.7	283.3

Fig. 12. Maximum excess delay vs. link distance on outdoor/indoor LOS/NLOS.

Fig. 14. CDFs of delay spreads of the local maxima beams with various HPBWs on all links.

Fig. 13. CDFs of delay spreads of the maximum beam with various HPBWs on all links.

Fig. 15. Mean delay spread of the maximum beam with various versus HPBWs of the beam on all links.

result. Normally, the narrower is the beam the fewer interacting objects are illuminated by the beam and the shorter is the DS. The analysis indicated a clear inverse proportionality between the HPBW and the both time dispersion parameters.

Impact of the beam shape is evaluated with a finer HPBW granularity in Fig. 15. There the mean DS of both the maximum beam and local maxima beams are plotted as the function

of HPBW. We can observe almost monotonically increasing mean DS with HPBW increasing from 1° to 70° . Moreover, as a curiosity, we can observe that mean and median curves start converging with increasing HPBW, i.e., the probability distribution function of DSs becomes more symmetric with wider beams.

V. DISCUSSION

We have used a simple 3GPP beam pattern with constant -30 dB side-lobe level, embedded it on measured propagation paths and analysed resulting delay spreads and maximum excess delays at approximately 140 GHz radio frequency. Our intention is to give insight into expected radio channel characteristics of future upper mm-wave radio links and to provide time dispersion statistics for the radio interface design. Design aspects such as equalizer length, sub-carrier spacing, and CP length are determined by the expected maximal time dispersion of the radio channel.

We used 30 dB power threshold to cut weaker paths after the inclusion of beam weights. DS and MED statistics are presented in various categories combining indoor/outdoor, LOS/NLOS, and three link distance classes. The median DS and MED of all potential beams over all measured links with 10° HPBW are 8 ns and 95 ns, respectively. The corresponding median values without beam impact, i.e., with an isotropic antenna, are 23 ns and 198 ns, respectively. Evidently, such narrow beam pattern has a substantial impact on practical time dispersion characteristics. We also showed the HPBW versus DS trend of how the narrowing beamwidth yields shorter time dispersion.

Future work: The measurement data have been extended to double directional using ray tracing methods [14]. We have started conducting analysis of those data as well. There, instead of only single directional azimuth beam steering, beams are formed at both link-ends in both azimuth and elevation dimensions. We expect to some extent smaller time dispersion parameters from that analysis, since even fewer propagation paths will be illuminated by bi-directional beams as compared to the current single directional azimuth-only case.

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